

Incorporating cost considerations into shared decision-making: lessons from Bulgaria

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Abstract

This study aims to explore the need for and acceptability of incorporating treatment costs into shared decision-making (SDM) among patients and healthcare providers (HCPs) in Bulgaria.

This study is a qualitative, non-interventional evaluation of patients' and healthcare professionals' needs, acceptability, and perceived barriers to introducing the cost dimension into SDM in routine clinical practice. The study was based on data collected through focus groups and semi-guided interviews conducted separately with both patients and HCPs.

In total, the interviews involved thirteen HCPs (two oncohematologists and two hospital pharmacists; five physicians and one nurse from a multiple sclerosis (MS) clinic; and three endocrinologists), as well as eight oncological patients, six MS patients, and four diabetic patients.

SDM is not a well-known concept among Bulgarian HCPs and patients. However, they use it in an unstructured manner. Both groups agreed that SDM is an important approach in mutual communication that improves treatment outcomes and enhances patient adherence. Patients who are required to make co-payments consider SDM discussions that include cost information as very important, while those whose treatment is fully reimbursed consider it less necessary. Participants agreed that digital tools supporting SDM and including the cost dimension should provide objective, evidence-based information and be validated. While digital tools can be useful in providing information, patients valued direct communication with physicians, which should not be replaced by tools.

Keywords

shared decision-making, cost of therapy, digital tools, patient awareness, healthcare professionals' awareness

Introduction

Shared decision-making (SDM) is a relatively new concept of communication between healthcare professionals and patients. It involves the mutual exchange of information regarding various treatments and care options, their outcomes, side effects, and possible constraints and costs. The information could pertain to prevention, diagnostic and therapeutic methods, cost of therapy, and even the option of non-action (HAS 2013).

Shared decision-making is recognized by many authors as an important step in enabling patients to increase their responsibility in their therapy by directly participating in the treatment process. Making informed decisions from the patient's side is not a simple task and requires education and the establishment of mutual trust. Physicians and other healthcare professionals must be capable of convincing patients of the importance of their role in the decision-making process, explaining in sufficient detail the pros and cons of approaches, ensuring trust and deliberation in discussion, and arriving at a mutual decision regarding the related consequences (Stiggelbout et al. 2015).

The conversation brings together the clinician's expertise—treatment options, evidence, risks, and benefits—with the patient's preferences, personal circumstances, goals, values, and beliefs (NHS England 2019). Evidence suggests that individuals engaged in SDM are more likely to adhere to evidence-based treatment regimens (Lan et al. 2025; Ahijón Lana et al. 2025), have better health outcomes, and are less likely to regret the decisions made (Stacey et al. 2017). Integrating patient preferences into health policy is crucial to ensuring that treatments align with patient needs and expectations (Chen et al. 2025).

In the United States (US), SDM was supported by the Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act (ACA), enacted between 2009 and 2010, which endorsed its use as a communication model in healthcare settings among policymakers, providers, and patients (Perez Jolles et al. 2019). SDM can serve as a foundation for informational campaigns, fostering open dialogue between healthcare providers and patients to encourage informed choices and increase vaccine uptake. Since 2019, shared clinical decision-making about human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination has been recommended for adults aged 27 to 45 in the US (Sandya 2024).

In the digital era, numerous tools have been developed to support patient participation in healthcare decision-making. They provide balanced information on available options and help people reflect on and communicate their values and preferences. Patient decision aids do not recommend one option over another, nor are they meant to replace healthcare professional consultation. Instead, they support values-based, informed decisions with healthcare providers (NICE 2021).

While SDM continues to expand across various treatment areas, the integration of treatment cost is rarely included in discussion. Cost has been evaluated in SDM for depression in Malaysia—where health coverage influences the comparison of prices (Zaini et al. 2018)—and in the US, where cost of treatment appeared among the top five

priority questions to discuss during SDM sessions (Barr et al. 2016; Streufert et al. 2017). However, such studies are limited in most European countries, including Bulgaria, which motivated our interest in the topic.

This study aims to explore the need for and acceptability of incorporating treatment costs into SDM among patients and healthcare professionals in Bulgaria.

The study is part of the *Next generation health technology assessment* (HTx) project—patient-centered, societally oriented, real-time decision-making on access to and reimbursement of health technologies throughout Europe—financed by the Horizon Europe program (<https://www.htx-h2020.eu/>). It covers a planned study within Work Package 5 (WP5): qualitative evaluation of the acceptability of, and barriers to, introducing the cost dimension into SDM at clinical sites. This manuscript presents results from the study conducted by the Bulgarian team at Medical University–Sofia, following the WP5 methodology developed by François Houÿez, Julien Delaye, Zsuzsanna Ida Petykó, Mohsharif Nasrulloeva, and Bertalan Nemeth.

Methodology

Design of the study

This study is a qualitative, non-interventional evaluation of patients' and HCPs' needs, acceptability, and perceived barriers to introducing the cost dimension into shared decision-making (SDM) in everyday clinical practice. In addition, the interviews included questions on the importance of effectiveness and safety, as well as digital tools that incorporate cost information to support SDM.

The study was based on focus groups and semi-guided interviews with patients and HCPs led by the researchers involved in the project. The current paper presents results obtained in Bulgaria, with plans for subsequent papers to compare findings from all participating countries.

Participants—inclusion and exclusion criteria

Patients under consideration were those with multiple sclerosis, selected rare oncological diseases (e.g., oncohematological diseases in Bulgaria), and type 1 or type 2 diabetes, as these groups were expected to differ in severity. Diseases were selected according to those targeted in the HTx project. HCPs included in the focus groups had corresponding specialties.

HCPs were recruited using a purposeful sampling approach, including a 'snowball' strategy to identify suitable providers. The process began with potential participants from the research team's professional contacts, followed by invitations extended by a co-author at the clinical center. HCPs were asked to recruit at least one patient and provide them with an information letter about the study.

The focus groups included around 8 (6–10) HCPs and patients from each disease area. They were interviewed together

(HCPs in one group and patients in another) because they had a common experience or held particular expertise on the topic of interest. We used the focus group method as it encourages participants to discuss and explore questions. Such groups can serve multiple purposes, such as discovering opinions, gathering information, and understanding behaviors.

Inclusion criteria to participate in the focus groups were to treat or to suffer from the disease of interest, to possess a smartphone, tablet, or laptop, and to be able to use such technology (for the purpose of on-site polls). Patients and clinicians did not need to be experienced with the shared decision-making concept or familiar with computer-based decision aids. The exclusion criteria were (1) inability to speak, read, or write the language of the country in which the study is conducted (in our case, Bulgarian), (2) failure to provide informed consent, and (3) being under the age of 18 years.

Focus group interviews

The focus group interviews were performed in three steps:

1. Introduction (approximately 10 minutes): Participants signed the informed consent, learned about the study subject, and provided basic information about themselves;
2. Concept presentation (approximately 20 minutes): The concept of shared decision-making and cost of treatment was introduced. A computer-based SDM aid and cost-related information were presented by qualified and experienced researchers leading the focus groups;
3. Questions and answers in a formal setting: Participants discussed how comfortable they would be discussing benefits, side effects, and the cost of treatment, including aspects of health coverage.

Themes discussed are presented in Appendices 1 and 2.

Data processing and analysis

Interviewers provided a summary of the transcript of the focus groups. Two participants read the transcript and systematized the answers according to their similarity, relevance to the questions, and the thematic framework discussed.

A comparative table was created for the answers—separately for HCPs and separately for patients (Tables 2, 3). Answers were compared in a logical manner to identify the need for, acceptability of, and feasibility of introducing the cost of treatment into SDM.

Ethical considerations

All data were collected anonymously after participants signed the informed consent form, including agreement to publish the results. The Ethical Committee at the Medical University of Sofia approved the study (Decision No. 987/27.02.2024).

Results

The interviews involved a total of 13 healthcare professionals and 18 patients – Table 1.

Interview with the HCPs

Summarized results from the interviews with healthcare professionals (HCPs) are presented in Table 2. In response to the first question about their knowledge of the shared decision-making (SDM) concept, most HCPs reported limited prior familiarity but considered such discussions very important in daily clinical practice. The most frequently discussed topics with patients included therapy duration, expected outcomes, efficacy, safety, alternatives to therapy, and the importance of medication adherence. The cost of therapy is rarely addressed in oncology and multiple sclerosis (MS) care due to the availability of reimbursement coverage. In contrast, endocrinologists indicated that treatment cost is a regular topic of discussion.

In recent years, younger patients with diabetes have become more informed and active in the decision-making process, while in rare and oncological diseases, the decision is mostly driven by HCPs. All physicians noted that, while patients' opinions and preferences about therapy are considered, the final treatment choice is based on clinical guidelines and the patient's condition (Table 2).

Computer-based tools for SDM are perceived as useful by physicians when there is a need to provide answers to frequently asked questions about efficacy and safety. Digital tools are considered the future for younger generations, particularly in cases of multimorbidity and complex therapies, according to endocrinologists and MS specialists. In contrast, oncologists observed that patients rarely discuss therapy cost, and digital tools would mainly be useful to answer disease-related questions. A surprising finding was that patients often discussed treatment cost not with physicians but with hospital pharmacists. These discussions concerned not only the price but also the availability of the therapy, underscoring concerns over supply shortages. It may be assumed that, in such cases, patients are willing to pay a high price for medicines because they value treatment success (Table 2).

Table 1. The amount of interviews with healthcare professionals and patients.

	Oncohematology	Multiple Sclerosis	Diabetes
Patients	8	6	4
Healthcare professionals			
Physicians	2	5	3*
Hospital pharmacists	2	–	–
Nurses		1	

*The diabetes focus group included one endocrinologist, one internal medicine specialist, and one gynecologist, with the latter two regularly treating diabetic patients in their everyday practice.

Table 2. Interview with healthcare professionals.

Questions/Answers	Oncohematology	Multiple sclerosis	Diabetes
Have you ever heard about shared decision making (SDM)?	Only at a theoretical level, but never as a practical application. We never participated in such decisions. In general, after evaluating the patient's status and disease stage, we discussed possible treatment options, but competent decision-making is left in the physician's hands. Most patients, of course, trust our proposal for their therapy. In the pharmacy, patients ask about prices. They also ask what new alternatives are coming—new approved options for their disease and dosage regimen for prescribed medicines.	SDM is essential in our practice, though we might not always use that exact terminology. We involve patients in every decision, explaining appropriate therapies based on factors like age, gender, desire for children, and disease activity. Patients need to participate; otherwise, adherence to therapy becomes challenging. For instance, we would not prescribe an injectable form if a patient fears needles. We avoid a paternalistic model and always consider the patient's preferences. The primary aspect is to comply with guidelines.	Every day in our practice, we collaborate with patients to make informed treatment decisions. Unfortunately, I have noticed an increasing number of young patients with diabetes in recent years. They often inquire about how diabetes medications will interact with their other health conditions and express concerns about cost. Overall, we work together to determine the best treatment options. They often come quite informed (using different sources like the Internet, etc.).
What do you think about the computer-based supporting tools for SDM?	There is no clarity whether SDM concerns what physicians offer from the medical aspect or some pharmacoeconomic aspect. In most cases, according to physicians' experience, patients never ask them about the medicine price. Patients ask mainly about medical aspects, such as duration of therapy, side effects, when therapy will stop, discharge timing, when the next infusion is scheduled, whether the therapy should continue in the same modality, and other common questions during anamnesis. In the pharmacy, patients ask about prices when they receive their medicines.	These tools are helpful, especially from the patient's perspective. While we have not used such platforms in our clinic, they seem interesting. Patients could use them to come to us with specific questions. Testing these applications would be beneficial. Technology is undoubtedly the future, and young people are particularly connected to such applications. The interviewer will share the link. It helps determine the appropriate treatment based on specific patient factors.	This is the future. Computer-based support tools for shared decision-making (SDM) will be time-saving and beneficial as sources of information, particularly for patients with multiple health conditions and medications and elderly patients who rely on caregivers. We believe that age is no longer a barrier to using these technologies, as more and more elderly patients are becoming comfortable with smartphones and applications.
How do you feel about such a computer-based supporting tool for SDM, compared to current discussions with patients? How do you think that such a tool could help in choosing appropriate treatment during SDM?	For the elderly patient, it is difficult to manage with digital tools. But digital tools are accessible to younger people. If the patient demands some information, I do not see any reason to deny providing it. As part of the shared responsibility in society, the necessity of providing more information to the patients about their state, therapy, cost, etc., is discussed. I rarely discuss with my patients (2nd physician), and when the therapy is reimbursed, I never discuss the price. We mostly consider the guidelines for the therapy, international and Bulgarian pharmacotherapeutic guidelines. The price is somewhat out of the guidelines, and effectiveness as well as safety are the leading reasons for choice. Effectiveness concerning the progression-free survival, overall survival, and response are the leading reasons for choice, and the price is outside these reasons.	Reimbursement statuses for MS drugs vary by country. Here, we follow a 1st and 2nd line therapy basis. Even if the application recommends a highly effective therapy, national specifics may limit our options. For instance, one patient chose to switch doctors because she wanted more than just computer-generated information; she wanted direct doctor interaction. Therefore, these tools are aids, not substitutes for doctors.	Yes, we think they will be helpful in patients with multiple health conditions, or patients who are at high risk of adverse drug reactions or drug interactions.
How can patients and doctors discuss which treatment is chosen? Is information on relative efficacy useful? How can side effects be compared? How do you view the discussion of the relative costs of treatment options? Do you find it informative at this stage? Do you think it should always be considered? Do you feel comfortable discussing the cost of treatment when discussing the efficacy and safety of different treatments?	Physicians said that they never discuss the price with patients. In the pharmacy, patients ask if they can buy it themselves to feel free from any mis-supply and fear of not having therapy. When patients asked, we explained to them that it is a very specific medicine, 100% reimbursed. They cannot take it from the community pharmacy, only from a hospital pharmacy with a prescription. There are many additional therapies, and if the price is high, many patients with other diagnoses are nonadherent.	Patients need to know the cost to engage actively in their treatment. When treatments are fully reimbursed and cost nothing out-of-pocket, some patients may take them for granted and not adhere properly. Knowing the price could motivate them to stick to the therapy and appreciate the efforts to improve their condition.	Patients should be informed about the efficacy of their treatment options, as this information can sometimes outweigh financial concerns. We discuss various treatment options with patients, including co-payment details. Patients need to understand the various treatment options available to them, as well as the costs they will need to cover. This knowledge can greatly influence their adherence to the treatment plan, and patients' preferences for therapy type, drug formulation, and financial issues should always be considered by the physician. Having tools that can display different treatment options and co-payment information would be beneficial, time-saving, and transparent for decision-making. One of the most frequently asked questions is related to the cost of therapy.
If you had the opportunity to advise the HTx researchers on whether or not treatment costs should be discussed during a general decision-making consultation, what advice would you give?	If the patient needs such information, we should not deny it. In the past, part of the documents that patients signed was the medicine list, which at the end had systematized information about the price. Nowadays, such documents are not needed.	Knowing the price could motivate patients to stick to the therapy and appreciate the efforts to improve their condition. The cost-benefit ratio is crucial. Decision-making starts with efficacy, safety, and patient condition discussions. Price is important, but secondary. Pharmacoeconomics is not often applied in hospitals and outpatient practices.	Eventually, these computer-based tools should be refined to align with various therapeutic indications, ensuring that they meet the specific needs of different medical conditions. Furthermore, it is essential to integrate these tools into established pharmacotherapeutic guidelines so that healthcare professionals can utilize them effectively in their clinical practice, enhancing patient care and treatment outcomes.

Questions/Answers	Oncohematology	Multiple sclerosis	Diabetes
Do you have any comments, amendments or corrections to this summary?	From the point of view of regulatory control, it is necessary for patients to see that they receive a particular therapy at a particular price. This is also an important reason to discuss the price. If patients receive other medicines, there are 2 aspects—some patients receive additional therapy during their hospital stay, which is 100% reimbursed, but in an outpatient situation, there is a co-payment, and patients very often ask for prices when they have to buy their medicines or co-pay. This is especially true for older patients and if they have additional costs such as dietary, food supplements, travelling expenditures, etc. Elderly patients have additional diseases that are not related to oncological diagnosis. We can say that for patients, it is important to discuss the price when there is a co-payment or additional medicines, and for them, the price is an important element.	SDM and digital tools are very useful. Patients should be familiar with them. Cost discussions should come last, as health is invaluable, but everyone must engage in this dialogue with rights and obligations. Digital tools should be shared with patients, but decisions should result from in-depth dialogue with doctors. Tools are aids, not replacements for doctor-patient communication. SDM is essential for therapy adherence and shared responsibility. Computer technologies are the future, but they cannot replace communication with doctors. They help convince patients. Price is important but should be discussed to ensure adherence.	No
Did we miss anything? Do you think we missed anything in the discussion? This is the first in a series of similar groups we are doing. Do you have any advice on how we can improve?	As physicians, we are mostly concerned with effectiveness, safety, protocol requirements, etc. We do not make our decisions based on many factors but mostly follow the patient's characteristics and the guidelines for therapy. There are many new medicines, and we have a choice, but it is not based on the price. For us, the price of therapy does not have the same weight as effectiveness, safety, limitations of treatment, and guidelines.	Achieving desired therapeutic results is a collective effort of a multidisciplinary team.	No

The perceived need for computer-based SDM tools varies among physicians, but most expressed a positive view. They noted that if patients request more information and wish to use such tools, there should be no barrier to access. Digital tools may be particularly needed for multiple conditions with a high risk of adverse drug reactions or drug interactions. These tools should be adapted to the local language and the conditions of the healthcare system.

The next set of questions focused on the usefulness of SDM and the relevance of cost-related discussions in treatment decisions. Oncologists did not consider cost issues to be relevant for SDM due to full reimbursement. In contrast, the other HCPs, including hospital pharmacists, considered such discussions relevant for increasing patient awareness of societal costs, motivating adherence to therapy, and influencing patient preferences regarding alternative therapies. The availability of tools that display different treatment options and associated co-payments could save time and increase transparency in decision-making.

HCPs advised the project team to align the digital tools with the available therapies, integrate them with treatment guidelines, and provide information about efficacy, safety, and the cost of different options, along with more in-depth pharmacoeconomic data.

Additional comments emphasized that digital tools should support, not replace, communication between HCPs and patients. They should equip physicians with arguments and motivation but not substitute for personal interaction. From a regulatory standpoint, digital tools should inform patients about treatment prices and, in the case of older patients with comorbidities, should help manage co-payments. Physicians also stressed that while decisions are based on clinical guidelines and patient characteristics, achieving successful treatment outcomes requires joint effort.

Interview with the patients

Summarized results from the patient interviews are presented in Table 3. Almost all patients had not heard of the SDM concept. Oncology and MS patients primarily rely on the physician's choice of therapy. Some patients even shared that they feel anxious when reading medical information online, but the same information, when explained by a physician, feels less intimidating. Diabetic patients also prefer face-to-face conversations, including those related to SDM and therapy costs. The perceived objectivity of computer-based tools was seen as a way to broaden their understanding of their condition.

The second question, although broad, revealed patient preferences regarding knowledge about the effectiveness, safety, and cost of therapy. For oncology patients, treatment effectiveness is the primary concern, followed by safety, depending on the severity of adverse reactions. Cost is generally a lower priority. One oncology patient mentioned a willingness to pay out-of-pocket to avoid losing workdays due to long travel distances to treatment centers. Patients with MS expressed interest in cost-related issues but were aware that their therapy is fully reimbursed. They fully trust their physicians' therapeutic choices and show little concern about costs. One patient recalled being asked for a co-payment at the pharmacy, which was ultimately covered by the drug manufacturer. In Bulgaria, for expensive and biologic medicines, producers occasionally offer discounts to wholesalers to cover patients' co-payments. Nonetheless, MS patients would be more concerned about costs than oncology patients if they were required to co-pay. In contrast, SDM and discussions about therapy costs were important for diabetic patients, as most of their therapies involve co-payments.

Table 3. Interview with patients.

Questions/Answers	Oncohematology	Multiple sclerosis	Diabetes
What are your thoughts about the computer-based aids for SDM? Any questions or remarks?	Not all patients have heard about SDM, but some commented that it is always shared. Physicians propose, and patients say whether they will agree or not. Rather, physicians give advice, and the answer is more likely yes. We discussed with a physician about taking the tablets, right? Up to this point, shared decision-making has been beneficial for making the final decision. Regarding the computerized tool, patients said that it is good to some extent, but it is not good to some extent. When patients read everything, they get scared. When the physician explained that it is calmer for patients to discuss it. Patients prefer direct contact with a physician; even some children have forbidden reading what is written about the illness on the Internet. When I read it on the computer, I feel scared, while when I discuss it with you, I feel calmer. I think a computer tool will be very useful. As long as they reach the people who need them. It will be an aid, but I prefer the discussion with a doctor. Because I have great trust in the doctor I am being treated by. He cannot replace the doctor in any way. Digital tools give a chance of avoiding errors.	This is the first time we have heard of it. P1: They say what the therapy is, and I agree because I do not know what it is. I came to change the medicine. They explain to us what is good, and we trust them. We do not come pre-acquainted. Doctors know best. P2: I am on injections. I do not like it because it leaves marks and pain. And I talked to the doctors; they did tests and said that it is not good to change medicine because it works. Regardless of the inconvenience, I continue the treatment. I cannot risk changing the treatment. The decision taken is shared, but mainly the doctors are the leaders. P3: Based on my condition, I trust the doctor, but we have not discussed the different options. I do not mind further discussion, but as soon as he has considered a certain treatment, I agree. I do not care if there are other options. P4: Comp-based tools are a nice approach as long as there are no subjective influencing factors. But it would be very useful. P5: The doctor does not discuss the options with me; he tells me what is best, and I agree with him. I think a comp-based tool would be helpful. I would use them for my illness.	P1. I prefer face-to-face communication; I am afraid that some of the computer-based technology could be a type of hidden advertisement. P2. As a term, no, but when visiting my physician, I always participate in some way. I might experience some technique issues with the tools, but the world is going in this direction, so we have to stick in and learn as it would be definitely beneficial. P3. Will help. P4. I do not understand the computers.
Is the information on relative efficacy helpful? Is the information on side effects helpful? Is the information on the cost of treatment helpful? Do you find it informative at this stage? Do you think it should always be considered when choosing a treatment? Do you feel comfortable discussing the cost of treatment with your doctor/patient? Does it matter who pays? First case: when the cost of treatment is entirely covered by the social insurer (e.g., UK NHS), with no out-of-pocket payment? Second case: when a patient needs to pay part of the cost, e.g., 5% or 30%? Does the cost information invoke an altruistic reaction ("I do not want to cause a big cost to a strained system")? Does the cost information make patients feel like they are being pressured into choosing lower-cost care? And how does this differ from the situation where the patient pays some or all of the cost?	Positive, and certainly this would be like some kind of reassurance for the patient and some greater certainty. The information would also give the patient greater determination. For example, what we discussed about weight gain as a side effect of my treatment was important to me. Both the positive and negative sides of the treatment are important. Me: How would side effects be important to you when choosing a treatment? Would they tip the scales? When there is information, a person can judge what is more important to them. This was important to me as a side effect, but it would not make me refuse treatment. So efficacy is more important to you than side effects? In my case, I am interested in the cost of treatment. I am from far away and have to travel, and I was interested in whether I can buy it myself and how much it would cost. Because I have to be absent from work, and I am worried about how my employer would react if he knew I was sick. I would be interested in how much my treatment costs. For me, cost is always a supplement. Because if you search for my disease, for example, you will find a mass of recommendations, and what they are. I am not sure that I want artificial intelligence to tell me what to do. Which is more important to you – efficacy or side effects? Yes, both are important. Would side effects be a reason to refuse treatment? - It depends on what the side effects are. If they are temporary and do not worsen my quality of life. If I am being treated and they are constantly increasing, then I will think about whether they are not more important. In Bulgaria, my treatment is covered by the health insurance, but if I go abroad, I have to pay for it. So I was wondering how much it would cost here. It is not bad to know the amount, but it is not important to me. If he had to pay for it, it would be more important to me. Would you be embarrassed to ask the doctor what the costs would be, how much the treatment would cost? I would not be embarrassed to ask. But the treatment is more important than the price itself. Would you choose another medicine, or would you rather rely on what you already have information about? - What I know, I would accept more easily in this case. I do not know how much the price would determine my decision. A medicine with a similar type of efficacy and toxicity, each of us would choose the one that will be covered by the health insurance fund. Saying that I will not pay for the given medicine does not mean that I do not care how much the state pays. I think it is right to discuss the treatment with the patient, to discuss the side effects and for the patient to be fully aware of what he will receive and accordingly what is paid for, so that he will also receive it as an opportunity. So, I have always been informed before about my treatment method, what is ahead of us and what I will receive, and it has always been discussed between doctors and patients. We have discussed things mutually. Or specifically in cases where there is a possibility for a therapy to be chosen, to comment with the patient, that is, to have the patient have an opinion on what the treatment should be in your specific case. Everything new that can be done is good to discuss, now in this case, I do not think we have a large choice of treatment options and especially for our disease in Bulgaria.	Patients: It will be useful if they give it to us. They do not always give it. We read on the internet about side effects. The doctors tell us to tell them if we have an ADR. We do not know if it can be signaled to another. P1: I suppose yes, that it would be useful to be informed. P1: We ask if the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) takes over, and then we check on the Internet. My medicine is BGN 2,600. I need to know what the costs are. P2: I did not care what the costs were. Medicines are 100% reimbursed. It is not important to me what the price is. Patients started sharing what medications they are taking. P3: Whatever the doctor says it is. I trust it regardless of the cost. However, we should always be informed about the price. P4: I would not say, because for 17 years my therapy has been free and I expect it to be like that in the future. It depends on who needs this information for the price, not for me as a patient, but for the NHIF; the country, maybe. If the patient is paying extra, I would be interested in what the cost is. I do not care how much the NHIF pays. P5: It would be helpful but not essential. For me, it is important to have efficacy and results of treatment, and then there is the price. But it is good to comment. To choose the most suitable, with more benefits, fewer risks. The price is in last place, but if I have to pay, it will be prohibitive. I would be interested in the cost if not 100% reimbursed. Does it matter who pays? First case: when the cost of treatment is entirely covered by the social insurer (e.g., UK NHS), with no out-of-pocket payment? Second case: when a patient needs to pay part of the cost, e.g., 5% or 30%? P1: We are interested in who pays, and if there is an additional payment. There is no real co-payment for our medicines. 5 months ago, the pharmacy asked me for an additional payment of BGN 500, but it turned out that the company covers the difference. P2: I do not communicate with the doctor about the price; I am not interested in this information. At the beginning of the treatment, I asked the doctor if the NHIF would cover the treatment, but without asking about the exact price. Patients: No, we do not feel. We also pay for health insurance. It can happen to anyone. To allow the drug to be reimbursed, they have considered that they can cover the expenses and help the patients. Does the cost information make patients feel like they are being pressured into choosing lower-cost care? And how does this differ from the situation where the patient pays some or all the cost? Patients: If the doctor says the expensive medicine is better, we will take it. But it also depends on the price difference. Efficacy and safety are the most important. We trust the doctor. P6: I prefer the one with better quality. If I have to pay for the therapy, I will prefer the cheaper one, even though health is the most important.	P1. I think any information on the cost or efficacy of therapy is helpful. I often discuss the therapy cost with physicians, as the medicine is serious. Nowadays, there are similar medicines with different prices, which require preliminary discussion. The medicines paid by NHIF and reduced out-of-pocket payment are preferable. P2. Yes, I think that this information is also important for patients, especially those with multiple morbidities, like me. I would feel more confident if discussing this with my physician. Considering the cost, in my opinion if patients are financially engaged with the treatment, they will be stricter in following their therapy. Of course, I discuss the cost of therapy with my physician and give my opinion on the co-payment, especially when having a lot of medicines. P3. The information is extremely helpful. I always discuss the cost with my pharmacists. If I have to copay I am interesting about the opportunities. If the product is 100% reimbursed I might just be curious about the price. P4. I do not discuss the prices, my child is buying me the medicines. She always buying what physicians prescribe.

Questions/Answers	Oncohematology	Multiple sclerosis	Diabetes
If you had a chance to advise on the HTx project on whether the cost of treatment should be discussed during a shared decision-making consultation, what advice would you give? Let us recap our discussion for today. We aim to get your opinion on evaluating the need for and acceptability of discussing cost-effectiveness at the clinic.	We think that a computer-based assistance application will be helpful if it provides information about the efficacy of the treatment, which is more important than the side effects. When discussing treatment, patients want to receive information about the effectiveness of the treatment and about the side effects. The effectiveness is more important. Every medicine has side effects. It would be interesting to know the cost. You need to have such a discussion. Such a computer-based application would be useful to you, but you prefer the discussion with the doctor; you want to receive information about the effectiveness and side effects; you would not be bothered by asking the doctor about the costs. I have been in the hospital for more than 8 months, and for me, discussions with the doctor are of paramount importance for a person to go through this path. In our case, the question about cost is not relevant, because I have not paid anything for the treatment, and no such discussion has been held. I think that a person will give absolutely everything for health. I have even thought about selling my apartment and so on. If you have the opportunity to give us advice on this project regarding whether the costs of treatment should be discussed or not, during the general consultation for decision-making, what advice would you give me? It is good when doctors and patients trust each other, then discussing the therapy, discussing the entire treatment and discussing further actions in case of possible relapses, as in our case, I think it is good to do. For today, our goal is to get your opinion on assessing the need and acceptability of discussing profitability in the clinic, that is, in your opinion, it is good to discuss how profitable the medications we offer are. Of course, it is necessary. So far, I have no concerns about efficacy and everything I am treated with.	P1: Maybe do the same survey with the same people to see if their opinion has changed. It is good to ask people and judge what behavior is. P2: As for costs, I do not think they need to be discussed at all. For us, costs are not important, we do not pay. And it is important to study which is the most effective drug. P3: The study is interesting and beneficial to patients. Our needs and attitudes must be evaluated.	P1. I think patients should be informed obligatory for the therapy cost. P2. It would be nice to prepare some educational materials about different digital and computer-based tools for SDM that could be in favor for the patient, to understand better their aim and benefits P3. It should be discussed all cost options. The cost-effectiveness is something that the patients do not understand. It matters to regulators. P4. I want to know the cost and how much I have to copay.
Do you have any comments, amendments, or corrections to this summary?	No	It is good the doctors ask us if we can afford to pay for the medicine. It is important to discuss the treatment options; the price is not decisive for me at this stage because it is covered fully by NHIF. If there is a co-payment, then it is important to discuss it. It is good to discuss, of course. Computer-based tools would be very useful for the patient to be informed. To find a cure, there is a cure, but many people lose out on it. The treatment decision should be shared to catch the weak points in the treatment; discussion about the treatment is important. What I want to summarize is to find a solution to make patients feel good, to find a treatment that is not supportive, but to cure us. Then there will be no costs. It is useful for the doctor and the patient to discuss and apply shared decision-making and to use computer-based tools. Costs should not be put on the agenda when the NHIF covers 100%. If we have to pay, it should be part of the issues the doctor discusses with us.	P1. No P2. No P3. No P4. No
Have we missed anything? Do you think we have missed anything in the discussion? This is the first in a series of groups like this that we are doing. Do you have any advice for how we can improve?	If the patient is not going to pay for it, it is not necessary to know the cost. The patient is more likely to be worried at this point.		No for all patients.

Patients offered several recommendations for the project regarding the content of a computer-based SDM tool. For oncology patients, effectiveness information should be prioritized, but cost information is also relevant, particularly for those considering alternative treatments abroad. They suggested that the study be repeated in broader disease groups and expressed interest in the final results of the current study. Moreover, patients recommended that educational materials about digital SDM tools be developed and distributed in the national language.

Additional issues raised by patients involved the affordability of therapy relative to available alternatives. Price is not a decisive factor when treatment is fully covered, but an informed patient may still wish to compare options. Patients emphasized that treatment decisions should be shared between the patient and the physician to identify

weak points in the therapeutic approach. They also expressed greater concern about achieving a cure than about discussing supportive treatment options. If out-of-pocket payment is required, patients believe that treatment costs should be discussed with their physicians. Physicians, in turn, should be trained to respect and incorporate patients' preferences and needs into the decision-making process.

Discussion

In this study, we attempted to reveal patients' and HCPs' needs, acceptability, and perceived barriers to introducing the cost dimension into shared decision-making (SDM) in everyday clinical practice across three disease areas in Bulgaria. As the first study of its kind in Bulgaria, it

offers a framework for understanding and promoting readiness among both HCPs and patients to adopt SDM and integrate it into routine practice. Both groups agreed that SDM is an important approach to communicate not only knowledge but also fears and expectations related to therapy, particularly in the context of rare and oncological diseases. Our findings align with those of the World Health Organization (WHO), which demonstrated its commitment to advancing SDM by publishing a systematic review exploring factors that influence SDM in the Eastern Mediterranean Region, thereby emphasizing its relevance across diverse healthcare settings (Alsulamy et al. 2021). SDM has broad applicability across medical specialties—for example, in neurology for conditions such as Alzheimer's disease (Aye et al. 2025), in dermatology for hormonal acne treatments (Smith 2025), and in anesthesiology for selecting appropriate anesthesia in hip surgery. Furthermore, SDM holds potential for influencing areas such as medical malpractice litigation by shaping patients' decisions about legal actions (Durand et al. 2014).

Both patients and HCPs in our study emphasized that information on treatment effectiveness and safety is of primary importance, with cost considerations ranking third. This prioritization applies not only to SDM but also to the use of digital tools for communication between patients and physicians, especially for elderly individuals with comorbidities. Clear information on expected treatment outcomes can improve adherence and positively influence patient behavior. Similar findings were reported in a systematic review demonstrating that SDM interventions significantly improve outcomes for disadvantaged populations (Durand et al. 2015). SDM increased patient knowledge, reduced decision conflict, and benefitted individuals with lower literacy more than those with higher literacy. A survey of over 63,000 respondents also indicated that poor SDM is associated with worse physical and mental health outcomes, lower adherence to recommended treatments, and increased use of emergency services (Hughes et al. 2018). An online survey in Italy highlighted the importance of raising women's awareness and education regarding symptoms and treatment options for uterine fibroids, promoting greater involvement in SDM and potentially leading to earlier diagnoses and better outcomes (Petraglia et al. 2025). Similarly, SDM was shown to reduce hospitalization days for patients with peritoneal dialysis by offering home-based treatment options tailored to patients' needs (Park et al. 2024). Regulatory institutions such as the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) in the United Kingdom have recognized the benefits of SDM, incorporating it into NHS policy since 2010 and supporting its implementation through guidance, training, and patient decision aids (NICE 2018; Couter et al. 2022).

In our study, cost concerns were more prominent among patients who are required to make co-payments compared to those receiving fully reimbursed therapies. This is expected, as the latter two groups suffer from life-threatening or debilitating diseases for which treatment is entirely covered. This observation supports the

notion of moral hazard in the context of full coverage. A study from Romania used vignettes to simulate real-world decision-making under different insurance conditions, providing insights into patient behavior and preferences that enhance SDM (Hutu et al. 2024). A U.S.-based study found that having detailed cost discussions between cancer patients and healthcare providers was associated with a 33.8% reduction in average total out-of-pocket expenses, highlighting the financial benefits of incorporating cost conversations into routine care (Coylewright et al. 2020). Other research indicates that out-of-pocket costs significantly influence treatment decisions in patients with heart failure and reduced ejection fraction (Smith et al. 2019; Dickert et al. 2025). In a retrospective study, patient education about osteoporosis led to a decrease in willingness to pay out-of-pocket for anti-osteoporotic therapy (Deng et al. 2024). A UK study assessing cost information's impact on treatment choices for sore throat, psoriasis, and sciatica found that itemized tariffs led participants to prefer lower-cost treatments, while flat fees increased the selection of higher-cost options (Chan et al. 2014). Integrating cost discussions into SDM can thus improve trust and satisfaction, resulting in both cost savings for patients and broader reductions in healthcare system expenditures (Chan et al. 2014; Wohlegemuth et al. 2019; Hoque 2024; NHS England 2024).

A key component of our study was the introduction of digital tools to support SDM by providing information on treatment effectiveness, safety, and cost. In general, both patients and HCPs had a positive view of these tools, although concerns were raised about the objectivity of information. Therefore, digital tools should be developed under the guidance of HCPs and validated by patients to ensure alignment with users' needs. It is advisable to involve patients in the development process from the earliest stages. Additional barriers include language issues and disparities in access to medicines and care across countries. As such, digital tools should be nationally oriented and support—but not replace—physician–patient communication, which was identified as a third concern.

Regarding the comments from HCPs, digital tools have the potential to improve transparency and inform on all existing treatments that are authorized in the EU, even if some are not reimbursed or not available in Bulgaria. When national decisions (to deny reimbursement or limit access to a product) are justified, there is no risk in mentioning the existence of these other treatments. On the contrary, when information is hidden, users (here, the patients and the prescribing clinician) might question the objectivity of the tool.

Some decision-support tools can be personalized, allowing patients to enter their own characteristics to receive individualized predictions on which treatment may be most effective for them. Interviewed patients in our study expressed an interest in such tools and, in general, in more information. An 8-year study assessed clinician use of personalized patient decision aids (PDAs) integrated into patients' electronic health records (EHRs). The findings demonstrated sustained and growing utilization

among clinicians, with high adoption rates, particularly in primary care, and positive feedback regarding convenience and support for shared decision-making. The results suggest that embedding decision aids into the EHRs can effectively address common implementation barriers and promote consistent use in routine clinical practice (Coylewright et al. 2020).

The study by Claessens et al. (2025) examined the implementation of the Assessment of Burden of Chronic Conditions (ABCC) tool in Dutch primary care through interviews with 17 healthcare professionals. Major barriers included the complexity of digital environments, lack of integration into existing guidelines, time constraints, and patients' reluctance to engage actively in their care. Facilitators were a clear understanding of the tool's benefits, its compatibility with current practices, and a supportive work culture that encourages innovation (Claessens et al. 2025). Some of the results in this study were confirmed by our interview as a need to align the tools with differences between various available therapies, integrate them with guidelines, and provide information about the efficacy, safety, and cost of different options, as well as more in-depth pharmacoeconomic knowledge.

Despite growing international support, numerous barriers continue to hinder the widespread adoption of SDM, and they must be addressed before full integration into healthcare practices in these countries (Alsulamy et al. 2021). In Canada, although implementing national healthcare strategies faces ongoing challenges, the government continues to provide funding for various SDM programs (Légaré et al. 2022). Additionally, in many countries, the COVID-19 pandemic may have had a negative impact on SDM by eliminating decision-making options due to urgent public health mandates, but it also stimulated new research and the development of decision support tools (Köther et al. 2021; Légaré et al. 2022). Our study shows that patients are less proactive, rely more on physicians' decisions, and participate less actively in SDM. Evidently, liability and informed consent play a crucial role in the context of SDM for interviewed patients. It is necessary to continue exploring this topic and to work on integrating SDM in clinical practice and the legal framework in Bulgaria. While SDM overlaps with informed consent, it extends further by focusing more deliberately on the individual needs and values of each patient. Although it has the potential to strengthen patient–clinician relationships and reduce liability through improved communication and documentation, it may also introduce risks if not properly implemented. To mitigate these risks, clinicians should stay informed about local regulations, use up-to-date decision aids, and carefully document the SDM process (Lindor et al. 2016).

While our study is based on an international methodology, it is nationally oriented, which represents a limitation. Patients and HCPs in Bulgaria appear to have limited knowledge of SDM, although they practice it in an unstructured way. Based on the results, we recommend that policymakers establish a supportive framework and standards for implementing SDM in clinical practice while

also educating patients about its possibilities and process. This might include cost-related discussions to enhance patient adherence, ensure truly informed consent, and ultimately improve treatment outcomes. Another limitation is that we included patients familiar with electronic devices. Therefore, the benefits and usefulness of digital SDM tools are limited to this specific group of individuals.

Conclusion

Shared decision-making is not a well-known concept among Bulgarian healthcare professionals and patients. However, they use it in an unstructured way in clinical practice. Both groups agreed that SDM is a valuable communication tool that can enhance treatment outcomes and improve treatment adherence. Patients with co-payments consider SDM discussions that include cost information as very important, while those with full reimbursement consider it less important. Digital tools for SDM, including cost-related aspects, should be designed to provide objective and validated information. While these tools can support informed decision-making, patients emphasized that direct communication with physicians is extremely valuable and cannot be substituted by any tools.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The ethical committee at the Medical University of Sofia approved the study with decision 987/27.02.2024.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

GP—design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, writing; MK—design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, writing; KT—data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, writing; MD—data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, writing; TC—data collection, data analysis, writing; YS—data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, writing; VS—data collection, data analysis, data interpretation; MDo—data collection, data analysis, data interpretation; BN—methodology, design, data analysis; ZP—methodology, design, data analysis; FH—methodology, design, data analysis. All authors approved the final text.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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Appendix 1. Possible questions for groups of patients

What are your thoughts about the computer-based aids for SDM? Any questions or remarks?

Key questions

Is the information on relative efficacy helpful? Is the information on side effects helpful?

Is the information on the cost of treatment helpful?

Do you find it informative at this stage?

Do you think it should always be considered when choosing a treatment?

Do you feel comfortable discussing the cost of treatment with your doctor/patient? Does it matter who pays?

First case: when the cost of treatment is entirely covered by the social insurer (e.g., UK NHS), with no out-of-pocket payment?

Second case: when the patient needs to pay part of the cost, e.g., 5% or 30%?

Does the information on cost invoke an altruistic reaction (“I do not want to cause a big cost to a strained system”)?

Does the information on cost make patients feel like they are being pressured into choosing lower-cost care?

And how does this differ from the situation where the patient themselves pays some or all of the cost?

Ending questions

If you had a chance to give advice to the HTx project on whether or not the cost of treatment should be discussed during a shared decision-making consultation, what advice would you give?

Let us recap our discussion for today. Our aim is to get your opinion in evaluating the need for and acceptability of discussing cost-effectiveness at the clinic.

Concluding briefly, this is the summary of our discussion. The main points that I can extract are... Do you have any comments, amendments, or corrections to this summary?

Final question Have we missed anything? Do you think we have missed anything in the discussion? This is the first in a series of groups like this that we are doing. Do you have any advice for how we can improve?

Appendix 2. Possible questions for healthcare providers

- 1.1. Have you ever heard about shared decision-making (SDM)?
- 1.2. What do you think about computer-based supporting tools for SDM?
- 1.3. How do you feel about such a computer-based supporting tool for SDM in comparison with current discussions with your patients? How do you think that such a tool could help in choosing appropriate treatment during SDM?
- 1.4. Key questions: How can patients and doctors discuss which treatment is chosen? Is information on relative efficacy useful? How can side effects be compared? How do you view the discussion of the relative costs of treatment options? Do you find it informative at this stage? Do you think it should always be considered? Do you feel comfortable discussing the cost of treatment when discussing the efficacy and safety of different treatments?
- 1.5. Closing questions: If you had the opportunity to advise the HTx researchers on whether or not treatment costs should be discussed during a general decision-making consultation, what advice would you give? Let us summarize our discussion for today. Our aim is to get your input in assessing the need and acceptability of discussing cost-effectiveness in the clinic.
- 1.6. In conclusion, this is a summary of our discussion. The main points I can draw from this are... Do you have any comments, amendments or corrections to this summary?
- 1.7. Last question Did we miss anything? Do you think we missed anything in the discussion? This is the first in a series of similar groups we are doing. Do you have any advice on how we can improve?